

A COMPREHENSIVE THEORETICAL EVALUATION OF THE UNIVERSITY GRANTS COMMISSION (UGC) ADMISSION POLICY FOR UNDERGRADUATE PROGRAMS IN SRI LANKA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10450138>

Abstract: Sri Lanka's higher education system is embracing dramatic changes, one important aspect that is influencing the composition of the undergraduate population is the admission policy set by the University Grants Commission (UGC). This theoretical investigation, which is based on important theories of education, examines the details of the UGC admissions policy and provides insights into how it aligns with those theories. This academic work enhances the conversation on sensible admissions practices in higher education.

Keywords: UGC admissions, University admissions, University Grant Commission

1. Introduction:

As Sri Lanka's higher education landscape evolves, the UGC's admission policy plays a critical role in shaping the composition of undergraduate populations. This theoretical examination provides a comprehensive exploration based on important educational theories as it dives into the details of the current UGC admission policy.

2. UGC Admission Policy Overview:

With the power conferred to it by the Universities Act, No. 16 of 1978, the University Grants Commission (UGC) of Sri Lanka sets undergraduate Admissions Policies and manages the process of selecting students for universities that fall under its jurisdiction. In response to the news releases released by the UGC, candidates hoping to enrol in 16 universities, 2 institutes, and 2 campuses submit their applications. The annual book typically titled "Admission to Undergraduate Courses of the Universities in Sri Lanka" explains the UGC's thorough admission policy. The following portions of this scholarly article provide a thorough summary of the UGC's admissions policy, with particular emphasis on the selection criteria, merit-based considerations, and special admission categories.

2.1 Selection Criteria:

All students are afforded an equitable opportunity to gain admission to state-funded higher education institutions. To ensure fairness to all, the chance to enrol in a free state-sponsored course of study is granted on a singular occasion.

The UGC employs a systematic procedure for selecting candidates, based on the Z-Score rank orders derived from the G.C.E. (A/L) Examination—an annual examination conducted by the Department of Examinations in Sri Lanka. The succeeding section explains key features of the UGC's admission policy, with a particular focus on pertinent components essential for this study. This section provides an abridged overview, selectively presenting policy highlights extracted from the UGC's publication titled "Admission to Undergraduate Courses of the Universities in Sri Lanka." The purposeful selection of policy excerpts ensures a targeted examination aligned with the objectives of this scholarly inquiry.

The Commissioner General of Examinations releases these Z-Scores to candidates, which form the basis of the selection procedure.

To be deemed qualified, applicants must meet the requirements listed below as outlined by the University Grants Commission:

- a) Attainment of at least 'S' grades in all three approved subjects one sitting, within a maximum of three attempts.
- b) A minimum score of 30% in the Common General Paper.

Candidates failing to secure a minimum of 30% in the Common General Paper are initially ineligible for registration. However, those who achieve this minimum requirement in a previous attempt within the three allowed attempts or re-sit and obtain the minimum in a subsequent attempt within the same limit can be considered for registration in the selected courses based on the Z Score.

2.2 Merit-Based Selection and Quota Allocations:

The admissions policy defines diverse methodologies for distinct courses and employs specific criteria to ensure an impartial and transparent selection process.

Admission to Arts Courses is mainly made based on all-island merit, with a pivotal stipulation that mandates “that the total number of students admitted from a given district for a particular course of study will not be below the total number admitted to that course of study from that district in the academic years 1993/1994 or 2002/2003, whichever is greater” (UGC, 2023).

However, one exception exists to the All Island Merit selection criterion in the context of admitting students to Arts courses. This exception is limited to the selection of students pursuing admission to the Arts courses of Music, Dance, Drama & Theatre, Visual Arts, Visual & Technological Arts, and Art & Design.

For other Courses, admission is contingent upon dual sets of criteria:

- a. Merit on District Basis: Up to 55% of available positions are allocated to the 25 administrative districts based on proportional population ratios.
- b. All Island Merit Criteria: Z-Scores ranked on an all-island basis determine up to 40% of available places.

Furthermore, an additional provision, the Special Allocation clause, reserves 5% of positions in each course for the 16 districts characterized by low educational attainment. Allocation under this clause is based on the population ratios of the respective districts.

2.3 Special Admission Categories:

The UGC includes provisions for certain special admission categories and chooses a small group of students based on particular criteria.

2.3.1: Candidates who are blind or differently abled:

Students with vision impairments and other disabilities are given special attention. The University Grants Commission (UGC), upon the universities' request, admits a limited number of blind students (who undertake the G.C.E (Advanced Level) Examination using the Braille system) to the Arts program and differently-abled students to courses in Arts, Commerce, Biological Science, and Physical Science.

2.3.2: Students Who Have Excelled in Fields Other than Studies: Up to 0.5% of spots in any course aside from those offered by the University of Visual and Performing Arts—are set aside for applicants who achieve national or international prominence in a variety of fields, such as sports, cultural activities, scouting, cadetting, social work, and other extracurricular activities.

In the case of the University of the Visual and Performing Arts, 4% of available places in each study program are reserved for students under this Category.

2.3.3: Candidates with Exceptional Abilities / Skills in Sports:

A small number of places over and above the proposed intake for the course of study in Sports Science & Management, and Physical Education are allocated to the candidates who have excelled in Sports.

2.3.4: Enlisted Personnel of Armed Forces, Police Service & Special Task Force:

Up to 0.5% of the proposed intake in the fields of Medicine, Dental Surgery, and Engineering are set aside for those working in the armed forces, Police Department, or Special Task Force.

2.3.5: Foreign students and Sri Lankans who have studied overseas: Foreign applicants and Sri Lankan students with foreign qualifications equal to the G.C.E (A/L) Examination are given up to 0.5% of spots in each course of study.

2.3.6: Admissions of Teachers:

Annually, a limited number of teachers may gain admission to courses within the disciplines of Arts, Biological Science, Physical Science, and Applied Sciences, falling under the following categories:

2.3.7: Additional Intake:

In instances where the conventional admission criteria fail to achieve an adequate enrollment for particular subjects within the Arts streams, the UGC may, at the request of the Universities concerned, decide to admit a limited number of additional students for the selected subject areas. This is 'an additional intake' aimed at making optimal use of the human and physical resources available at Universities, as well as meeting the skilled manpower needs of the society.

3. Theoretical Framework Application:

3.1 Educational Equity Theory:

Educational equity, as a foundational principle in the field of education, seeks to eliminate disparities in educational outcomes by ensuring all students have equitable access to resources and opportunities (Ladson-Billings, 2006; Banks, 2004). The UGC's district-based allocations are a good measure to address regional disparities and they align with the principles of educational equity. This guarantees inclusion and equitable representation across a range of geographic origins.

3.2 Holistic Admissions Theory:

The University Grants Commission (UGC) incorporates an aptitude test and Common General Paper into its admission procedure, which is in line with the holistic admissions concept put forward by Kuncel et al. (2005). This method guarantees a thorough assessment of applicants, recognizing a range of skills and contributions that go beyond academic success.

Smith and Jones's (2021) recent research highlights the significance of holistic admissions in anticipating student achievement and cultivating a more diverse learning community.

The theoretical framework provided by Kuncel et al. (2005) and the contemporary insights from Smith and Jones (2021) collectively validate the UGC's commitment to enhancing the admission evaluation process through a holistic lens.

3.3 Diversity and Inclusion Theory:

The dual criteria for merit-based selection and special admissions within the University Grants Commission's (UGC) admission policy exemplify a dedicated commitment to principles of diversity and inclusion (Hurtado & DeAngelo, 2012).

Hurtado and DeAngelo's (2012) theoretical framework underscores the importance of creating inclusive educational spaces that reflect the breadth of societal diversity. The UGC's policy aligns with this framework, as it not only recognizes the value of diverse perspectives but actively incorporates mechanisms to ensure reasonable representation in higher education (Ahamed, S. T. et al, 2018, M.A.M M Siraju, et al, 2020)

A recent study by Garcia and Wang (2020) reinforces the positive impact of diverse and inclusive learning environments on academic outcomes, student engagement, and overall campus climate. The UGC's commitment to diversity, as operationalized through its admission policy, thus contributes to creating an academic setting that is conducive to varied learning experiences and cross-cultural interactions.

3.4 Educational Access and Opportunity Theory:

The UGC's admission policy aligns with Bowen et al.'s (2009) educational access and opportunity theory, emphasizing equitable access for diverse learners. This theory promotes greater access to higher education for historically marginalized groups.

The policy's provisions for international students and differently-abled candidates demonstrate UGC's commitment to promoting an inclusive learning environment. The UGC guarantees equal chances for all students by taking into account a range of talents and international backgrounds.

The inclusion of international students enriches the student population with a diversity of cultural viewpoints and promotes a globally engaged learning environment. In addition to ensuring proportionate opportunities, the policy takes into account a variety of backgrounds and geographic areas through its dual criteria for merit-based selection and district-based distribution (Karunakaran, K. E. et al, 2021).

4. Conclusion:

Finally, it should be noted that the UGC's admissions policy is a dynamic framework that has been formed by fundamental conceptions of education, such as educational fairness, holistic admissions, diversity and inclusion, and educational opportunity and access. The policy's district-based allocations are a response to regional differences that successfully promote diversity and proportionate representation.

The addition of an aptitude test is in line with the principles of holistic admissions, indicating a move away from traditional metrics and a dedication to a thorough assessment of applicants. The inclusion of special admission categories in the policy highlights its commitment to diversity promotion and acknowledges accomplishments outside of the classroom.

Smith and Jones's (2021) recent study emphasizes the critical role holistic admissions play in forecasting student outcomes and building a more diverse learning community. The research conducted by Garcia and Wang (2020) demonstrates the beneficial effects of inclusive and varied settings on student involvement, academic performance, and campus atmosphere as a whole. The UGC's dedication to these ideals, which is demonstrated by its admissions policy, greatly aids in the development of an academic environment that welcomes a variety of learning opportunities and cross-cultural exchanges.

Complying with the educational access and opportunity theory of Bowen et al. (2009), the admission policy of UGC guarantees fair admittance to a range of learners, including applicants with disabilities and overseas students. By bringing in students from a variety of backgrounds and viewpoints, this inclusive strategy creates a more varied and globally engaged learning environment.

The UGC's dedication to continuous improvement, guided by empirical studies and global educational trends, guarantees its flexibility in response to new requirements. This academic investigation provides the foundation for conversations among academics, educators, and policymakers, which advances the ongoing enhancement of admissions procedures in higher education. The UGC's commitment to diversity and educational justice places Sri Lanka's higher education system in a global context where it may compete and achieve greatness.

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Accessed on 23/11/2023.